

Diseño de videojuegos sobre el patrimonio y su incidencia en las competencias digitales de los futuros docentes

Design of heritage-based video games and its impact on future teachers' digital competences

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RESUMEN. La competencia digital desempeña un papel central en la actual formación docente, y los estudiantes deben tener oportunidades estructuradas y equitativas para aprender a utilizar las tecnologías de manera creativa. Este estudio investiga el impacto del diseño de juegos digitales sobre patrimonio en las competencias digitales de estudiantes del Grado en Educación Primaria de la Universidad de Granada. Se usó un método mixto para evaluar las percepciones de los estudiantes antes y después de la intervención mediante cuestionarios ad hoc. Participaron 103 estudiantes. Los resultados mostraron un aumento en la autopercepción de sus competencias digitales artísticas (Mpre = 3.14, Mpost = 3.62) y técnicas (Mpre = 2.58, Mpost = 2.98) después de la intervención, pero no en las competencias digitales académicas. También se encontró una relación entre la experiencia previa con videojuegos y la competencia digital; los estudiantes que jugaban con frecuencia tenían percepciones más altas de sus competencias digitales.

ABSTRACT. Digital competence plays a central role in current teacher education, and students must have structured and equitable opportunities to learn how to creatively use digital technologies. This study investigates the impact of digital game design on heritage in the digital competences of students enrolled in the Bachelor's Degree in Primary School Education at the University of Granada. A mixed method was used to assess students' perceptions before and after the intervention using ad hoc questionnaires. A total of 103 students participated. The results showed an increase in the self-perception of their artistic (Mpre = 3.14, Mpost = 3.62) and technical (Mpre = 2.58, Mpost = 2.98) digital competences after the intervention, but not in academic digital competences. A relationship was also found between prior experience with video games and digital competence; students who played frequently had higher perceptions of their digital competences.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Competencias digitales, Educación patrimonial, Formación de docentes, Usos educativos de la tecnología, Videojuegos.

KEYWORDS: Technological skills, Heritage education, Teacher training, Technology uses in education, Video games.

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